

Effects of Myofascial Release Technique in Individual with Neck Pain – A Literature Review

¹Ni Made Candra Sari Praptiwi, ²Made Hendra Satria Nugraha

¹Bachelor of Physiotherapy and Physiotherapy Profession Study Program, Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University; praptiwi.2202541011@student.unud.ac.id

²Physiotherapy Department, Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University; hendra_satria@unud.ac.id

*Correspondence: praptiwi.2202541011@student.unud.ac.id (Ni Made Candra Sari Praptiwi)

Abstract

Neck pain is a health problem that is often faced by people all over the world. This condition can cause various movement and body function problems such as pain and decreased functional levels. The aim of this literature review is to determine the effectiveness of the myofascial release technique in improving pain and functional status in individuals with neck pain. This literature review uses 2 databases as sources, namely: Physiotherapy Evidence Database (PEDro) and PubMed/MEDLINE. The articles used in this study include: (1) Articles with randomized controlled trial (RCT) research designs; (2) Articles were published in the last 5 years (January 2020 - July 2024); (3) Articles must be in English. The initial search across two databases yielded 25 articles, of which 3 were duplicates and excluded. Applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 17 articles were selected. Full-text access was obtained for 15 of these articles. After assessing eligibility, 7 articles were deemed suitable for inclusion. Consequently, the study utilized a total of 7 articles. Data extraction was carried out by two separate reviewers. Risk of bias was assessed using a PEDro scale reviewed by two independent reviewers. The studies collectively included a total of 384 participants with neck pain. Intervention duration ranged from two weeks to four weeks. Various outcome measures were utilized to assess the effectiveness of the interventions, including the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and the Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) for pain assessment. The Neck Disability Index (NDI) and Neck Outcome Score (NOOS) are used to measure functionality or disability in neck pain. Based on the literature review, it can be concluded that myofascial release technique can improve pain and neck disability in individuals with neck pain by providing 5 – 8 therapy sessions with a therapy duration of 50 – 60 minutes.

Keywords: *myofascial release technique, neck pain, literature review*

INTRODUCTION

Neck pain is a frequently encountered condition in clinical practice and poses diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. Its prevalence is rising among the general population and specific subgroups worldwide. Although prevalence estimates vary, research indicates that 22% to 70% of individuals will experience neck pain at some point during their lifetime.¹ Neck pain is often linked to occupational factors such as long working hours, sedentary lifestyles, demanding jobs, poor computer workstation setup, and prolonged sitting. These conditions can lead to muscle tightness, reduced neck movement, and overall limitations in function. According to global disease burden statistics, the prevalence of neck pain is reported as follows: Asia at 10.14%, Australia at 10.13%, the Caribbean at 9.7%,

Southeast Asia at 7.6%, Central Asia at 9.8%, East Asia at 11.8%, Central Europe at 9.9%, Eastern Europe at 9.9%, and Latin America at 10.12%. In the Mediterranean region, specifically in Pakistan, the point prevalence of neck pain was estimated at 34.31 per 1,000.²

Commonly used conservative treatments for neck pain include medications such as pain relievers and muscle relaxants. Physical therapy approaches are also widely employed and encompass a variety of techniques. These include manual therapies like post-isometric relaxation, exercise programs focusing on stretching, strengthening, and endurance, thermal therapies (hot and cold applications), light-based treatments (laser and infrared), electrical stimulation (TENS and ultrasound), dry needling, and acupuncture.²

Myofascial Release Technique (MRT) is a therapy designed to alleviate tension in soft tissues caused by restricted fascia, the connective tissue surrounding muscles. In the neck, muscles like the trapezius and levator scapulae are commonly involved in this type of pain. These muscles often contain tender points called trigger points. Pressing on these points can cause significant discomfort. Myofascial release treatments aim to reduce musculoskeletal pain through various mechanisms, including potentially influencing the nervous system and the release of certain chemicals in the body.³

Through a comprehensive review of existing literature, this study aims to elucidate the efficacy of Myofascial Release Technique (MRT) in managing neck pain. The findings will provide evidence-based guidelines for clinical practitioners to optimize patient care.

METHOD

A. Search strategy

The systematic review involved searching journal databases like the Physiotherapy Evidence Database (PEDro) and PubMed/MEDLINE. The search strategy utilized keywords such as 'myofascial release technique' AND 'neck pain'. The PICO set are, P: neck pain, I: myofascial release technique, C: -, O: pain and neck disability.

B. Inclusion/exclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria include: (1) Articles with randomized controlled trial (RCT) research designs; (2) Articles were

published in the last 5 years (January 2020 - July 2024); (3) Articles must be in English. While the exclusion criteria include: (1) Other articles are excluded, if there is the same article; (2) abstracts, conference proceedings, case reports, or thesis.

C. Data extraction

Data extraction was carried out by two separate reviewers (NMCS and MHSN), and any discrepancies were settled through discussion. The study characteristics gathered included: (A) author information; (B) participant attributes such as age, gender, and sample size; (C) intervention dosage; and (D) outcome variables, with a focus on pain and disability parameters.

D. Quality assessment

Risk of bias was assessed using a PEDro scale⁴ reviewed by two independent reviewers (NMCS and MHSN) and any disagreements were resolved by discussion.

RESULT

A. Study selection

The initial search across two databases yielded 25 articles, of which 3 were duplicates and excluded. Applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 17 articles were selected. Full-text access was acquired for 15 of these articles. After assessing eligibility, 7 articles were deemed suitable for inclusion. Consequently, the study utilized a total of 7 articles. Study selection are described in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flow Chart of Identification of Studies

B. Methodological quality and risk of bias of reviewed studies

Explanation concerning the quality assessment in regards to the journals, described in table 1.

Table 1. Methodological quality of included studies using PEDro Scale

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Total Score
Khan, <i>et al.</i> , 2022	-	√	√	√	-	-	-	√	√	√	√	7/10
Corum, <i>et al.</i> , 2021	√	√	√	√	-	-	√	√	-	√	√	8/10
Shewail, <i>et al.</i> , 2023	√	√	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	√	√	3/10
Cabrera-Martos, <i>et al.</i> , 2020	√	√	√	√	-	-	√	√	√	√	√	8/10
Rodriguez-Huguet, <i>et al.</i> , 2020	√	√	√	√	-	-	√	√	√	√	√	8/10
Pérez-Martínez-Casero, <i>et al.</i> , 2020	√	√	√	√	-	-	√	√	√	√	√	8/10
Deshmukh, <i>et al.</i> , 2022	-	√	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	√	√	3/10

Source: (PEDro, 1999)⁴

C. Study characteristics

The characteristics of the study results are summarized in table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of reviewed studies

Author	Subjects	Intervention	Control/Comparison	Outcome Measure	Results
(Khan, <i>et al.</i> , 2022) ²	N=60 Males = 20 Females=40 Age range: 25-40 years Non-specific neck pain: 2-6 weeks	Post-isometric relaxation (PIR) with cryotherapy and isometric strengthening exercises. PIR applied for upper trapezius and levator scapulae. -Isometric contractions: 10 s, -Relaxation and gentle stretching: 10 s, -Repeated 5 times.	Myofascial Release Therapy (MRT) with cryotherapy and isometric strengthening exercises. MRT applied for upper trapezius and levator scapulae. - Resistance in contralateral side: 10 s - The head forward to increase the resistance for 10 s on Levator scapulae - Repeated 5 times.	VAS, NDI, Cervical Extension, left side rotation ranges, and QoL (Social Domain)	- PIR is more effective in alleviating NSNP than MRT within 2 weeks.
(Corum, <i>et al.</i> , 2021) ⁵	N= 39 Age range: 19-48 years	Cervical spinal manipulation and Exercise. Exercise. - Three days a week - Three sets of five to ten repetitions, - 30-to-60 s rest period between sets	Myofascial release group was performed for 8 sessions (twice a week for four weeks.	Headache frequency, VAS, NDI	- Manipulation group was statistically better in improving headache severity, headache frequency, and pain pressure threshold scores than myofascial release group.
(Deshmush, <i>et al.</i> , 2022) ³	N=100 Age range: 11-60 years	Myofascial release technique	Basic exercise therapy	VAS, NDI	- Pain on VAS and NDI score also showed significant improvement (p<0.05) in intervention group when compared to the controlled group. - Myofascial release techniques were more effective than general exercises in non-specific neck pain patients.

(Shewail, <i>et al.</i> , 2023) ¹	N=33 Age range: 18-25 years	Instrument-assisted soft tissue mobilization (IASTM)	Myofascial release therapy (MRT)	VAS, PPT, NDI	- There is no statistical significance between the two groups regarding improvement in pain, function, and PPT.
(Cabrera-Martos, <i>et al.</i> , 2020) ⁶	N=40	-	Neurodynamics and myofascial release	VAS, NOOS	- Pain severity, average pain, and some aspects of functionality improved significantly after the combination of neurodynamics and myofascial release.
(Rodríguez-Huguet, <i>et al.</i> , 2020) ⁷	N=54	Massage, Ultrasound therapy, and TENS	Myofascial Release Therapy	NPRS, PPT	- Myofascial release therapy could be better program for improving pain and suboccipital PPTs in patients with neck pain than a standard physical therapy.
(Pérez-Martínez-Casero, <i>et al.</i> , 2020) ⁸	N=58 Age range: 21-40 years	MRT	Self-MRT using INYBI	VAS, local pressure pain sensitivity, active CROM, pain-free vertical mouth opening	- Both INYBI and SMI methods were equally effective in reducing pain and increasing pain tolerance in adults with chronic neck pain. However, SMI showed slightly better results in improving neck movement, while INYBI specifically led to increased VMO activation.

CROM, Cervical Range of Motion; IASTM, Instrument-assisted Soft Tissue Mobilization; INYBI, tool for self-treatment of the suboccipital area; MRT, Myofascial Release Technique/Therapy; NDI, Neck Disability Index; NOOS, The Neck Outcome Score; NSNP, Non-Specific Neck Pain; PIR, Post-isometric Relaxation; PPT, Pressure Pain Threshold; QoL,

Quality of Life; SMI, Suboccipital Muscle Inhibition; TENS, Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation; VAS, Visual Analogue Scale.

Participant characteristics

The studies collectively included a total of 384 participants with neck pain. Participants' ages varied from 11 to 60 years old, indicating a wide demographic representation across different age groups. Some studies provided gender breakdowns, such as one study with 20 males and 40 females, suggesting a higher representation of females in certain studies. The studies included participants with neck pain and subjects of studies had varying sample sizes, ranging from as few as 33 participants to as many as 100, which can affect the generalizability of the findings. The duration of interventions varied, with some studies implementing treatment over two weeks to four weeks, which is important for understanding the effectiveness of the Myofascial Release Technique over time.

Intervention characteristics

The intervention characteristics are summarized in Table 2. Intervention duration ranged from two weeks to four weeks. These interventions included Myofascial Release Therapy (MRT), Instrument-assisted soft tissue mobilization (IASTM), neurodynamics, post-isometric relaxation (PIR), cryotherapy, and isometric strengthening exercises, among others. Many studies incorporated control or comparison groups that received standard physical therapy treatments, allowing for a comparative analysis of MRT's effectiveness against established methods.

The duration of the interventions varied, typically ranging from two weeks to four weeks, which is crucial for assessing both short-term and long-term effects of the treatments. Additionally, the frequency of treatment sessions per week was specified in some studies,

indicating that treatments might be administered two to three times weekly.

Outcome Measure

Various outcome measures were utilized to assess the effectiveness of the interventions, including Numeric Pain Rating Scale (NPRS) and Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain assessment. The Neck Disability Index (NDI) and Neck Outcome Score (NOOS) are used for measuring functionality or disability in neck pain.

DISCUSSION

Research involving the administration of myofascial release with the suboccipital inhibition technique applied for 8 sessions showed results that there was a significant increase in the improvement of neck pain and disability in individuals with neck pain. After 3 months of follow-up, significant results were seen on the neck pain disability scale measurements.⁵ In addition, other studies that combined myofascial release and neurodynamics showed significant results in improving pain and neck functional scales in individuals with neck pain. The intervention was given for 50 – 60 minutes per session per week for 4 consecutive weeks.⁶ Other research also confirms the effectiveness of myofascial release therapy in improving pain in individuals with neck pain. This study applied myofascial release therapy for 5 therapy sessions. The results of the study at 1 month follow-up showed an improvement in the NPRS score.⁷ Lastly, other studies also support that myofascial release techniques are better than general exercises in non-specific neck pain patients in terms of measuring neck pain and disability.³

In contrast to several previous studies, one study compared giving post-isometric relaxation to myofascial release

therapy. This research shows that providing post-isometric relaxation is better in reducing neck pain and disability at 2 weeks follow-up in non-specific neck pain.² Other studies comparing instrument-assisted soft tissue mobilization with myofascial release therapy also showed insignificant results in improving pain and disability in individuals with neck pain.¹ A study compared of myofascial release therapy with self-myofascial release therapy (INYBI) where the administration lasted 5 minutes with 1 therapy session. Measurements were taken 45 minutes after administering the intervention. The results showed that there was no significant difference in reducing pain between giving myofascial release therapy and self-myofascial release therapy.⁸

CONCLUSION

Based on the literature review, it can be concluded that myofascial release technique can improve pain and neck disability in individual with neck pain by providing 5 – 8 therapy sessions with a therapy duration of 50 – 60 minutes.

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